

DOD SPACE SYSTEMS DATA BASE

Mr. Richard B. Larson

Electromagnetic Compatibility Analysis Center
North Severn, Annapolis, Maryland 21402

ABSTRACT

There has been a significant increase in recent years in the utilization of spaceborne communications-electronics systems to perform a variety of functions including communications, navigation, and surveillance. This growth has resulted in increasing concern over congestion to the geostationary orbit and frequency spectrum. The DOD Electromagnetic Compatibility Analysis Center (ECAC) has been tasked to develop the required data base and analysis models to support future DOD space system planning. The project, begun at ECAC in 1981, consists of three major elements: data base design and software development, data compilation and analysis model development. As of January 1984, over 160 space systems had been identified and skeletal records describing these systems entered into an automated data base. Future efforts will concentrate on compilation of more detailed data for the data base and development of appropriate electromagnetic compatibility analysis models.

INTRODUCTION

There has been a rapid growth in recent years in the number of communications-electronics systems utilizing spaceborne elements. These systems perform a multitude of functions including communications, navigation, scientific measurements, weather monitoring, and surveillance. As the number of these space-based systems increase in both the military and civil arena, the competition for limited geostationary orbital positions and frequency spectrum is becoming a growing concern. This is evidenced by the convening of a World Administrative Radio Conference (WARC) in 1985 with the objective of "guaranteeing in practice, for all countries, equitable access to the geostationary orbit and to the frequency bands allocated to Space Services." It is clear that the DOD, because of its present reliance on satellite systems and the increased emphasis on these systems in the future, must be prepared to effectively plan its own electromagnetic spectrum growth and to effectively compete with other satellite requirements on the national and international level.

Effective planning of DOD systems requires a knowledge of existing and future satellite systems, not only of DOD systems, but of all systems in competition for the frequency spectrum and geostationary orbit. In June of 1981, the Office of the Under Secretary of Defense Research and Engineering, recognizing the lack of a central source of information within DOD regarding satellite systems, tasked the DOD ECAC to develop and maintain a space systems data base and analysis capability for the DOD.

Established in 1961, ECAC has the charter to develop and maintain information concerning the electromagnetic spectrum usage of communications-electronics systems for DOD, and to develop the required analysis capabilities to promote the electromagnetic compatibility (EMC) of DOD systems. ECAC was thus a natural choice for development and maintenance the space systems data base because of its previous experience in development and maintenance of terrestrial communications-electronics data bases, and its experience with development of EMC analysis models. The specific tasking of ECAC requested development of the data base include both military and commercial systems, emphasizing those utilizing the geostationary orbit. ECAC was requested to minimize the reporting burden on DOD and others by using existing reports and data bases to the maximum extent possible and to coordinate DOD's requirements with those of National Telecommunications and Information Administration (NTIA), Federal Communications Commission (FCC), and others to insure consistency, uniformity, and non-duplication of data requirements.

DATA BASE DESIGN

Initial development of the data base began in late 1981. The project consisted of three major elements: data base design and software development; data compilation; and analysis model development. The data base is being implemented on a SPERRY 1100/82, large scale computer, utilizing the SPERRY DMS 1100 data base management system. The data base design and software development tasks are being done in conjunction

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with a major upgrade of the existing communications-electronics characteristics data base at ECAC. This approach was taken due to the commonality of many of the data items in both the terrestrial and space systems data base and the cost savings to be realized by combining the efforts.

A space system, for the purpose of the data base development, has been defined as a group of cooperating satellites and earth stations. Earth stations include both fixed and mobile (airborne, land mobile, and shipborne) terminals. The space system data base is being designed to describe each system by using three (3) types of records; a systems level record; a space segment record; and an earth segment record (see figure 1). The systems level record contains a limited number of data elements and provides a general description of the system. This record consists of such data items as system name, ownership, function, frequency band, earth station types, number of satellites and geographic area of use.

The space segment data provides satellite technical descriptions, modulation descriptions and environmental information. A technical description is given for each on-board equipment such as transponders, receivers, transmitters, antennas, etc. Complete modulation descriptions are given for each transmitter and receiver. Satellite environmental information includes orbital descriptions and frequency assignment information for each satellite in the system. Orbital descriptions are obtained directly from the North American Aerospace Defense Command on magnetic tape and automatically entered into the data base.

The earth segment data follows the same general organization as the space segment. Each earth station type contains detailed technical characteristics of the transmitter, receiver and antenna along with complete modulation descriptions and earth station environmental information such as specific frequency assignments, locations, and host platforms in the case of mobile systems.

The specific characteristics which are contained in the data base were determined by an investigation of electromagnetic compatibility analysis requirements, data requirements for international frequency coordination and a survey of data currently contained in other automated data files. The data will be sufficient to perform intersystem EMC analyses but is not intended to be adequate to perform intra system EMC studies since this data resides with the developer who is usually responsible for this level of compatibility. A list of major data elements to be included in the data base is shown in Table 1.

FIGURE 1. SPACE SYSTEM FILE DESIGN

TABLE 1

Space Systems Data Base Elements

System Level Data Elements (Level I)

System Name
 Country/Consortium/Agency
 Satellite Names & Object Numbers

TT&C Information
 Uplink Frequency
 Downlink Frequency
 Sensor Wave Lengths
 Responsible Agency
 Network Identification
 Ground Sites

Mission Information
 Uplink Frequency Bands
 Downlink Frequency Bands
 Crosslink Frequency Bands
 Sensor Wavelengths
 Beacon Frequencies
 User Agency
 Satellite Equipment Nomenclatures
 Earth Station Equipment Nomenclatures
 Service Class
 Mission Function
 Geographical Area of use

Basic Technical Characteristics *
(Level II)

Carrier Frequencies
 Emission Designators
 EIRP
 Spectral Power Density
 Receiver Noise Temperature
 Channel Bandwidth
 G/T
 Antenna Gain & Polarization

*Note that these data elements will be compiled for each satellite and for each earth station type.

Comprehensive Space Data Elements
(Level III)

Operating Mode (s)
 Detailed Emission Descriptions
 Harmonic Emission Levels
 Spurious Emission Levels
 Transponder/Transmitter Output Power
 Transponder Gain
 Transponder/Receiver Noise Temperature
 Transponder/Receiver Saturation Level
 Receiver RF Preamplifier Gain
 Spurious Response Rejection
 Image Response Rejection
 Receiver Sensitivity
 Required S/N or E_b/N_0
 Receiver IF Stage Characteristics
 IF and LO Frequencies
 IF Bandwidth and Roll-off
 LO Injection Level
 Filter Characteristics

Type
 Center Frequency
 Bandwidth and Roll-off
 Antenna Beamwidths and Pattern Data
 Antenna Noise Temperature
 Earth Station Environmental Data
 Location
 Rain-Climatic and Radio-Climatic Zones
 Antenna Pointing Angles
 Specific Frequency Assignments
 Electro-Optical Equipment Characteristics
 Wavelength
 Radiant Emission Pattern
 Spectral and Spatial Emission Patterns
 Primary Line Width and Shape
 Equivalent Blackbody Temperature
 Emissivity
 Detector Type and Function
 Detector Responsivity
 Detector Geometry
 Detector Noise Current and Noise Bandwidth
 Effective Aperture Area
 Beam Divergence
 Transmittance and Transmittance Pattern
 Scan Rate
 Field of View
 Effective Focal Length

DATA COLLECTION

The data compilation portion of the data base development initially concentrated on collection of system level (Level I) records in order to get an idea of the magnitude of the collection effort and to identify data sources which may be valuable in the collection of detailed technical characteristics. This initial collection included identifying both current and future military, government, and commercial systems in geostationary and non-geostationary orbits. Future systems generally must be notified to the International Frequency Registration Board (IFRB) of the International Telecommunications Union (ITU) before being entered in the data base. This criteria was used to eliminate those "pie-in-the-sky" systems from cluttering the data base and expending effort on those systems which may never come to fruition. As of January 1984, over 160 space systems had been identified and described with system level records in the data base.

To support the DOD preparations for the Space WARC in 1985 and 1988, the next phase of the data compilation concentrated on collection of more detailed technical characteristics (Level II) of geostationary space systems. The data items to be collected were determined from a survey of analysis models which may be used to support the US preparations for the Space WARC. Collection efforts were prioritized to assure collection of data for geostationary systems in frequency bands of most concern to the DOD and the effort was coordinated with NTIA to assure that the parameters compiled were consistent with those being entered into their data base and would provide adequate data to support any analysis models developed for Space WARC 85 preparations.

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Upon completion of the collection of data for the high priority systems, plans are to compile Level II data for all geostationary systems followed by compilation of comprehensive (Level III data for all geostationary systems. Non-geostationary system data collection will follow the geostationary data compilation.

ANALYSIS MODEL DEVELOPMENT

The analysis model development is being accomplished concurrently with the data collection. Initial development efforts involved automation of international coordination models, specifically, automation of International Telecommunication Union (ITU) Radio Regulations Appendix 28¹ and Appendix 29². In addition, an effort to develop an automated model to predict satellite antenna coverage (footprints) has also been initiated. This model will be used to accurately determine the desired and interfering power levels on the surface of the earth for both geostationary and non-geostationary systems. The development of this model will be integrated with the data base compilation effort to assure that the data required to run the model is generally available and the data base structure can accommodate storage of the data.

In the coming year ECAC will conduct an analysis of future automated models required to supplement the above models and other models that currently exist. Current satellite analysis models will be reviewed for applicability to EMC analysis studies and a long term plan for implementation of appropriate models outlined.

AVAILABILITY OF SPACE SYSTEMS DATA

ECAC's services in regard to the space systems data base and analysis capabilities are available to all DOD organizations. Normally requests for data base listings are provided upon request to DOD organizations or to DOD contractors upon written authorization of the DOD sponsoring agency. Requests for services involving utilization of analysis models and manpower are handled on a cost reimbursement basis with charges determined on a case by case basis.

REFERENCES

1. Method for the Determination of the Coordination Area Around an Earth Station in the Frequency Bands between 1 GHz and 40 GHz Shared between Space and Terrestrial Radiocommunications Services, Appendix 28 ITU Radio Regulations 1982 Edition
2. Method of Calculation for Determining if Coordination is Required between Geostationary-Satellite Networks Sharing the Same Frequency Bands, Appendix 29 ITU Radio Regulations 1982 Edition